

Supplementary Figure S1. Translocation of ANN5 to pollen membrane (PM) followed by propidium iodide (PI) influx enables identification of pollen grains with deteriorated PM integrity.

Confocal image of pollen grains overexpressing *ANN5-YFP* incubated in 20% sucrose solution and stained with PI. The yellow arrowheads indicates exemplary pollen grain affected by osmotic stress, identified by binding of ANN5 to PM, but not yet stained by PI. A scale bar = 20 μm .

pLAT52:ANN5-YFP

Supplementary Figure S2. Spraying the pollinated stigma with water triggers ANN5 translocation.

(A) Fluorescence image showing hand-pollinated stigma with pollen grains overexpressing *ANN5-YFP*. (B) Image collected during pollen germination. (C) Image collected after spraying the pollinated stigma with deionized water. Stigma was sprayed three times at the approximate distance of 25 cm. (D) The enlarged images of the labeled regions (magenta rectangles) in section B and C. The fluorescence intensity profiles were measured along the yellow lines drawn from left to right.

pLAT52:ANN5-YFP

20% sucrose + 1.5 mM $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$

Supplementary Figure S3. Ca^{2+} application induces pollen grain bursting accompanied by ANN5 binding to PM.

Representative time-lapse images of pollen grains overexpressing *ANN5-YFP* acquired during incubation in 20% sucrose solution with the addition of 1.5 mM $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$. Pollen grains depicted with numbers (PG1-3) show a typical responses to the exogenously applied Ca^{2+} , accompanied by binding of ANN5 to the PM: pollen collapsing (PG1), rapid bursting (PG2), progressive bursting (PG3). Yellow arrowheads depict formation of a cap-like structure by ANN5 at the PM (PG3). Cyan arrow depicts PM-bound state of ANN5 in PG2. Magenta circle depicts cytoplasmic content released during PG2 bursting. A scale bar = 20 μm .

A*pLAT52:ANN5-YFP*

150 mM NaCl

propidium iodide

B**Supplementary Figure S4.** Pollen grains dehydration upon exposure to NaCl.

(A) Representative time-lapse images of pollen grains overexpressing *ANN5-YFP* incubated in 150 mM NaCl. Propidium iodide was used as counterstain to monitor the integrity of PM. Yellow arrowheads depict the site of ANN5 accumulation. Magenta numbers depict grains selected for the area measurement. Scale bars = 10 μ m. (B) Comparison of ANN5 distribution in pollen grains incubated in sucrose solution and in 150 mM NaCl. Scale bars = 5 μ m. (C) The normalized values plotted on the graph indicate a NaCl-induced decrease in pollen grain volume.

Supplementary Figure S5. ANN5 and ANN1 display a different affinity for PM under osmotic or ionic stress conditions.

(A) Confocal images of pollen grains overexpressing *ANN5-YFP* or *ANN1-YFP* collected during incubation under various stress conditions. Pollen grains were treated with 1.5 mM $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ or 1 mM MgSO_4 or 150 mM NaCl for 30 min. White or black arrowheads depict the site of pollen bursting induced by exogenously applied Ca^{2+} ions. Yellow arrowheads indicate local accumulation of ANN5 and ANN1 corresponding to the site of PM detachment from the pollen cell wall induced by Mg^{2+} . Scale bars = 10 μm . The fluorescence intensity profiles in section B were measured along the yellow lines drawn on the YFP images starting from left to right or down to up. The YFP fluorescence peaks denoted with magenta arrowheads correspond to the PM-associated pool of ANN5 or ANN1.

20% sucrose

Supplementary Figure S6. The effects of pollen germination medium ingredients on PM properties.

Confocal images of *Arabidopsis* (Col-0) wild-type pollen grains acquired after 30 min incubation in 20% sucrose solutions containing different compounds (1.5 mM Ca(NO₃)₂, 1 mM MgSO₄, 1 mM KNO₃ or 1.6 mM H₃BO₃), counterstained with fluorescent dyes: DiBAC4(3) (A) or DiOC(2)3 (B). Cationic DiOC(2)3 enters a cell due to its affinity for the negatively polarized membranes, and accumulates in the energized and negatively charged mitochondria. The anionic DiBAC4(3) is excluded by a polarized cell, because it is negatively charged and its influx into the cell cytoplasm indicates depolarization of the membrane. Scale bars = 20 μ m.

A

Supplementary Figure S7. Analysis of PI uptake by *B. napus*, *N. tabacum* and *M. domestica* mature pollen grains upon exposure to exogenous Mg²⁺.

(A) Confocal images of *B. napus* mature pollen grains incubated in 0.3 M mannitol solution with the addition of increasing concentrations of MgSO₄ and stained with PI. Plots of the changes in the pollen grains area induced by increasing concentrations of Mg²⁺. Grain area [μm^2] was measured for selected pollen grains on single confocal images acquired after 30 min incubation. $n \geq 50$ pollen grains in each solution. Kruskal – Wallis test with Wilcoxon test

was used for statistical analyses. Error bars depict standard deviation. Asterisks indicate means statistically significant, when compared to the control medium. *** p-value < 0.001. **(B)** Confocal images of *N. tabacum* and *M. domestica* mature pollen grains incubated for 30 min in 0.3 M mannitol solution with the addition of 5 mM MgSO₄ and stained with PI. Lack of PI staining in the majority of pollen grains. Scale bars = 20 μm.

300 mM mannitol + 5 mM MgSO₄

Supplementary Figure S8. Analysis of male gametophyte developmental stage-dependent sensitivity to Mg²⁺ ions.

Confocal images of Arabidopsis pollen grains of wild-type (Col-0) and overexpressing *ANN5-YFP* incubated in 300 mM mannitol solution with addition of 5 mM MgSO₄ for 30 min. Scale bars = 10 μm. **(A)** Mg²⁺ did not affect PM integrity in pollen grains from the late flower bud (stage 12) of wild-type and overexpressing *ANN5-YFP*, observed as a lack of PI staining. Compare with PI influx in lines silenced for *ANN5* in Supplementary Fig. S9. **(B)** Mg²⁺ induced membrane permeability for PI in mature pollen grain collected from open flowers (stage 13). Influx of PI was accompanied by ANN5 binding to the PM.

A300 mM mannitol + 5 mM MgSO₄ + PI

Supplementary Figure S9. Analysis of PI uptake in pollen grains from flower buds (stage 12) in Arabidopsis with modified *ANN5* expression levels.

(A) Confocal images of pollen grains of the wild-type Arabidopsis (Col-0), *ANN5*-RNAi knockdowns: line 13 and 15, overexpressing *ANN5-YFP* line 4 and 7 stained with PI. Images were collected after 30 min incubation in 300 mM mannitol solution with the addition of 5 mM MgSO₄. Scale bars = 20 μm. **(B)** Graph shows the fraction of PI-stained grains in the control solution and after exposure to Mg²⁺. Chi-squared test was performed on pollen grains exposed to Mg²⁺. p-value: ** < 0.01, *** < 0.001. n > 600 pollen grains.